

Evaluation of data augmentation techniques on subjective tasks

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Abstract

Data augmentation is widely applied in various computer vision problems for artificially increasing the size of a dataset by transforming the original data. These techniques are employed in small datasets to prevent overfitting, and also in problems where labelling is difficult. Nevertheless, data augmentation assumes that transformations preserve groundtruth labels, something not true for subjective problems such as aesthetic quality assessment, in which image transformations can alter their aesthetic quality groundtruth.

In this work, we study how data augmentation affects subjective problems. We train a series of models, changing the probability of augmenting images and the intensity of such augmentations. We train models on AVA for quality prediction, on Photozilla for photo style prediction, and on subjective and objective labels of CelebA. Results show that subjective tasks get worse results than objective tasks with traditional augmentation techniques, and this worsening depends on the specific type of subjectivity.

Keywords: Aesthetic Assessment, Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Data Augmentation

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1 Introduction

The term “Data Augmentation” refers to a collection of techniques aimed at generating synthetic data samples by either applying transformations to existing, real data samples; or by generating coherent data from scratch. Given the problems inherent to high-dimensional data [1], data augmentation is crucial in problems with this kind of data, especially in computer vision problems such as image classification or image segmentation. In these problems, augmentation can help by reducing the effects of overfitting caused by the curse of dimensionality: i.e., models trained on high-dimensional data tend to overfit more easily. Furthermore, some problems in computer vision do not have a wide range of data samples available. For example, in certain medical imaging problems, it is difficult to obtain image samples, due, among other factors, to the high cost of the equipment employed to obtain these images.

Most computer vision tasks can be considered to be objective. This is, the information to predict does not depend on subjective evaluations. Most cases of object classification, object detection and image segmentation can be considered examples of objective tasks. However, subjective tasks are also important in computer vision. One such task is aesthetic quality assessment, or AQA for short [2], a task that consists in automatically determining whether a given image/photography is “beautiful” or not. Even if this problem is subjective by nature, it has become of interest to the scientific community, since it has applications in which high-quality images are crucial, such as photo selection for advertising, sorting by quality in image retrieval systems, or even helping visually-impaired people choosing high-quality social network pictures.

Since the advent of deep learning for image classification in 2012, one of the most widely used datasets for solving AQA has been the AVA dataset [3]. This dataset contains nearly 255,000 images, and each image has received ratings from several users, where these ratings range from 1 to 10.

As Table 1 shows, AVA is still the largest-scale image aesthetics dataset available that offers such rich information as 1-to-10 ratings. Nevertheless, it is relatively small in size when compared with other datasets such as ImageNet [4]. Because of

this, in order to solve AQA using the AVA dataset, neural networks are usually fine-tuned on top of the weights of a feature extractor trained to solve image classification on ImageNet.

Another option for overcoming the small amount of images present in AVA would be to apply data augmentation techniques to generate more images. However, since aesthetic quality is a subjective characteristic, augmentation techniques could actually destroy the relationship between images and their scores, since rotating/scaling/colour-shifting the original images would alter the image features that make them aesthetically pleasant or unpleasant, as seen in Figure 2.

1.1 Research objective

The previously exposed points pose an interesting question: up to which point data augmentation techniques can affect subjective problems? There are many studies [5–8] that analyse the effects of data augmentation on objective problems (i.e., image classification, object detection, etc.). However, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study on the extent of the effects that data augmentation can have on subjective problems.

Not only augmenting images can alter their aesthetic groundtruths, but finding the correct set of augmentations for any given computer vision problem can be a time-consuming task. The set of augmentations to apply, their probabilities, and their intensities, are hyperparameters to be tuned, and finding the best configuration for a task adds additional overhead to the training process.

Motivated by these insights, the main aim of this work is to thoroughly study the effects of data augmentation on subjective tasks. By selecting some simple augmentation techniques, we conduct experiments by modifying the rate at which we apply our augmentation techniques. Furthermore, we apply these augmentation techniques for solving both subjective and objective problems, in order to compare the effects of data augmentation on these two different kinds of problems. The outline of this approach can be seen in Figure 1.

The rest of the work is organised as follows. Section 2 gives a brief overview of augmentation techniques and other AQA datasets. Section 3 details the augmentation techniques we will use

Fig. 1 Graphical abstract of our schema for comparing augmentation effects on subjective and objective problems. We employ subjective and objective datasets, and we apply 7 different augmentation techniques to each. For each dataset/technique combination, we run experiments by leaving a fixed intensity, and augmenting a specific percentage of all images.

Fig. 2 Example of the effects of data augmentation on aesthetic assessment. Note how the original image, a very high-quality photo, shown above, becomes a qualitatively worse photo by applying certain augmentation techniques, shown below.

in our experiments. Section 4 details the experiments we have run, together with their results and discussions. Finally, Section 5 presents the main conclusions of this work.

2 Related work

2.1 Augmentation techniques

In computer vision, data augmentation is usually necessary for complex problems whose datasets have a small amount of annotated images. The most widely-known augmentation techniques are based on either altering the spatial features of the image by applying simple techniques such as cropping, translation, zooming, etc., or on altering the colour features of the image by modifying the contrast, brightness, or other colour features [9]. In addition to these, there are techniques based on adding random noise to the images, and also on applying simple convolutional filters to sharpen, blur, or smooth the image, even though these last techniques are roughly equivalent to what the first layers of a regular CNN do [10].

Besides these classical techniques, some more advanced ones have been proposed lately. For example, [11] performs image augmentation by taking two images from the dataset, and overlaying one on top of the other, while keeping one of

Table 1 Information about various image aesthetics datasets [25]

	#images	Rating range
AVA [3]	≈ 255,000	1–10
Photo.net [17]	3,581	1–7
CUHK [18]	12,000	Binary
CUHKPQ [19]	17,613	Binary
AADB [20]	10,000	0–1
FLICKR-AES[21]	40,000	1–5
PARA [22]	31,220	1–5
TAD66K [23]	66,327	1–10
JenAesthetic [24]	1,628	1–100
BAID [25]	60,337	0–10

the original labels. Moreover, augmentation techniques based on deep-learning models have also been proposed. [12] apply style transfer to generate new images for training, and [13] discusses and studies various types of GANs to augment images for agriculture problems.

Furthermore, image augmentations can be applied to computer vision tasks that deal with videos. The authors of [14] apply simple augmentation techniques to generate synthetic videos for the video instance segmentation problem. Their results show that augmentation techniques are a promising venue for other video segmentation tasks, such as [15] and [16].

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Aesthetic Visual Analysis (AVA) dataset

The AVA image dataset [3] was created for solving image aesthetic assessment problems. As it is shown in Table 1, AVA is much larger in scale when compared to other datasets such as Photo.net [17], CUHK [18] or CUHKPQ [19]. Plus, it gives much more rich and complete labels in the form of 1-to-10 ratings. These two characteristics are our justification for choosing this dataset, even if, due to its scale, transfer learning is the only viable option for achieving good results.

AVA has around 255,000 photographs, taken by both amateur and professional photographers, with varying degrees of aesthetic quality. These photographs were obtained via web-crawling over the website www.dpchallenge.com, a website that hosts numerous photography challenges, covering a broad range of topics. The photographs submitted to each challenge receive ratings from 1 to

10 from the users of the website, who judge photographs by factors such as quality, adequacy to the challenge, etc.

Besides offering rich information, each image in AVA has a big amount of votes: 210 votes on average, between 78 and 549. In addition to this, AVA offers semantic information for each photograph, which is related to its specific challenge and photography style.

2.2.2 Photozilla dataset

The Photozilla dataset [26] is a large-scale image dataset created with the aim of detecting certain styles in photographs, such as aerial photos, architecture photos, event photos, etc. The goals of its authors, among others, are to help narrow-down results on image search engines based on specific styles, or recommending images based on preferences.

This dataset has around 990,000 images, categorised into 10 different photography styles, plus 10 more styles with 25 photographs each for performing few-shot learning. These images were obtained using the Flickr* API, where the photographs for each style were obtained by specifying such style as a tag to recover images.

2.2.3 CelebA dataset

The CelebA dataset [27] is a large-scale face attributes dataset, having more than 200,000 celebrity images from approximately 10,000 different celebrities. This dataset was originally created with the aim of predicting face attributes in the wild, and as such, these photos have a wide variety of poses and background elements.

Each photo is annotated with the presence or absence of 40 binary attributes. These attributes are highly varied, and range from objective attributes (presence/absence of glasses, neckties, earrings, etc.), to highly subjective attributes (attractiveness, big/small nose, big/small lips, etc.), making it an ideal candidate for our study.

2.2.4 Datasets justification

Even if it is a dataset from 2012, AVA is still the *de-facto* dataset for solving AQA, used in many recent papers [28–30]. Furthermore, it is

*<https://www.flickr.com/>

the best dataset in terms of scale and provided information, as other large-scale datasets do not provide aesthetics information as 1-to-10 user ratings. However, the main objective of this paper is to test the effects that data augmentation can have on subjective tasks. It is thus desirable to have a similar but objective dataset, in order to carry out a proper comparison.

To find such a similar dataset, it would need to have similar characteristics to AVA. More specifically, it would need to have a similar scale, similar images, and a groundtruth with a similar dimensionality. After careful consideration of various datasets, we opted for using Photozilla, since it is only 4x bigger than AVA, its images are also photographs, and it is a 10-class problem, just as AVA is a 10-rating problem.

Finally, to make our study more complete and for covering more than just photography datasets, we aimed for finding a dataset with subjective and objective characteristics, but of a different nature. After searching and analysing numerous datasets, we finally opted for CelebA, which is focused on face attributes rather than photography. It also has objective and subjective attributes in its attribute list, and is similar in scale to AVA.

3 Studied augmentation techniques

This section details the augmentation techniques we will apply in our studio. Since the aim of this work is to show how augmentation can affect model results on subjective problems, we will study some common, simple augmentation techniques. As per the taxonomy described in Figure 3, these common augmentation techniques can be divided into two categories:

3.1 Photometric augmentations

Photometric augmentation techniques are those that generate new images by altering the colours of the pixels of the original images. In our study, we apply two different photometric augmentation techniques:

- Random brightness change: the intensity values of each pixel are changed as per the following formula:

$$p = \text{clip}(p + (\alpha * \text{max_val} - \text{min_val}), \text{min_val}, \text{max_val}) \quad (1)$$

where α is a random brightness factor between -1 and 1, and min_val and max_val are the minimum and maximum allowed pixel values for the image; these can be in various ranges such as $[0, 255]$, $[0, 1]$, etc.

- Random contrast change: the contrast of the image is modified channel-wise by the following formula:

$$p = \text{clip}(\alpha(p - \mu) + \mu, 0, 255) \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha = U[1 - \text{min_val}, 1 + \text{max_val}] \quad (3)$$

where α is a random contrast factor, drawn from a uniform distribution between $1 - \text{min_val}$ and $1 + \text{max_val}$. These two variables have the same meaning as in the previous transformation. Finally, μ is the channel-wise average value.[†]

3.2 Geometric augmentations

Geometric augmentation has the objective of generating new images by altering the spatial composition of the original images, which is managed using simple linear transformations. These transformations modify the x and y position of the pixels of the original image, placing them into new x' and y' positions. In our study, we apply four such techniques:

- Random image flipping: with this technique, the image gets flipped either around its vertical axis or its horizontal axis, so the final value of the x -coordinate, the y -coordinate, or both, will be -1 times the original value. Assuming the origin of the image coordinate system is located at its middle point, this technique can be described by the following formula:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where both a and b control the axes that will be flipped, and can take either the value -1 to

[†]Note that, in the implementation of TensorFlow we are employing, values get clipped to the $[0, 255]$ range, instead of the real pixel range of the image.

Fig. 3 Taxonomy for our studied augmentation techniques. Inspired by the taxonomy at [9]

flip around the corresponding axis, or 1 to leave it as it is. a controls the flipping around the vertical axis, and b controls the flipping around the horizontal axis.

- Random image translation: this technique moves the pixels of the original image to new locations. All the pixels are displaced by the same amount, according to the following formula:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} T_x \\ T_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where (T_x, T_y) indicates how much each pixel will be displaced in the x and y direction, respectively.

- Random image rotation: this technique rotates the pixels of the original image around its centre. Also, assuming the origin of the coordinate system to be at the centre of the image, this transformation can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & -\sin(\varphi) \\ \sin(\varphi) & \cos(\varphi) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where φ is the angle by which the image will be rotated.

- Random image zoom: this technique scales the original images in both x and y directions by a

random amount on each one. Only pixels inside the original image dimensions are kept; the rest get discarded so as to keep the original image size. Assuming once again the origin of the coordinate system to be at the centre of the image, this transformation can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_x & 0 \\ 0 & S_y \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where S_x and S_y control the scaling factor on both the x and y directions, respectively.

Figure 4 shows some examples of the described augmentation techniques using one row per technique. The first two rows correspond to the photometric augmentations, and it can be observed how the spatial composition remains intact, but the colours get altered. The last four rows correspond to the geometric augmentations, where the spatial composition is getting distorted.

Note that both translation, rotation and zooming can cause pixels outside of the image to enter the new image. How these out-of-bounds pixels are handled depends on the implementation of the technique itself. In the case of the official implementation of the TensorFlow framework, it allows for either reflecting the image around the edges of

Fig. 4 Augmentation examples. Example base image extracted from the AVA dataset

the edge pixels, wrapping the image to the opposite edge, using the value of the nearest edge pixel, or using a constant fill value. For our experiments, we have opted for using a constant filling, since we consider that the other approaches can generate "weirder" images that will further degrade their aesthetic quality. Furthermore, as it is shown in the examples of [9], we opted for using a white filling, though we believe the effect of the fill colour on the final quality is negligible.

3.3 AutoAugment

In addition to these simple augmentation techniques, we also test the behaviour of AutoAugment [31] on both subjective and objective problems. This technique consists of a search algorithm that finds the best possible policy for augmenting images in a computer vision task, such that the model trained to solve such task achieves the best possible performance. In the original proposal, a policy consists of five-subpolicies, where each image is augmented by selecting a sub-policy at random. In turn, each subpolicy consists of two augmentations, applied sequentially, each one with a certain magnitude and probability of being applied.

While the authors have not disclosed the source code of this search algorithm, they have made public the policy that yields the best results for ImageNet, which is a concatenation of 5 high-performant policies. Furthermore, the authors show that this policy transfers well to other computer vision tasks. Therefore, we have tested the ImageNet augmentation policy in all our tasks.

4 Experiments and results

4.1 Experimental setup

The most trivial approach to performing the experimental evaluation is to train models on both Photozilla, AVA and CelebA via fine-tuning models pre-trained on ImageNet. However, even if this approach gives optimal results for these datasets in terms of balanced accuracy, those are not good for a fair comparison among them. Namely, these datasets present some traits that make it difficult to compare against themselves:

- While AVA and Celeba have only around 200,000 - 250,000 images, Photozilla has around 1 million images, roughly 4 times the size of these.

<i>Augmentation technique</i>	<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Low intensity</i>	<i>High intensity</i>
Brightness	factor	0.25	0.75
Contrast	factor	0.25	0.75
Flip	mode	horizontal	horizontal_and_vertical
Rotation	factor	0.25	0.75
Translation	height_factor	0.25	0.75
	width_factor	0.25	0.75
Zoom	height_factor	0.25	0.75
	width_factor	0.25	0.75
AutoAugment	—	—	—

Table 2 Parameter values corresponding to low-intensity and high-intensity augmentations. Note that the choice of values for the flip technique is due to convenience, so those values could have been given in any order.

- By pre-training on ImageNet, the high-level features learnt by a model are highly reusable for objective problems like Photozilla and most CelebA labels. For example, food photos may be identified by high-level filters trained to recognise food, of which there are actual ImageNet categories. However, for subjective problems such as AVA, these high-level features are much less reusable, since aesthetic quality is subjective, and ImageNet doesn't have a well-defined set of high-level filters which may help recognise it.
- Photozilla is a balanced problem: all classes are nearly equally represented on the dataset. However, AVA presents unbalance in the amount of each rating present in the dataset, in its mean score distribution, and in its binary form when splitting images on good/bad quality using a mean score of 5 as a threshold. Furthermore, depending on the label to predict, CelebA also presents unbalancing.
- The metrics given on the results in the AVA dataset are binary metrics. To compute those, the groundtruth ratings and the predictions must be split into two categories depending on whether their mean is above or below 5. However, Photozilla is a ten-class problem. Comparing a ten-class problem against a binary problem would be unfair. The other option would be to train AVA with a NIMA-like model: i.e., using EMD loss. However, this would not strictly be training a ten-class model, and it would still be an unfair comparison if training Photozilla as a ten-class problem.

All these traits give an unfair advantage to Photozilla, which reaches much better results than

AVA on the baseline scenario when training under the same hyperparameters. To perform a fair comparison, we have created ten one-versus-rest versions of Photozilla, taking a certain class as the positive class and the remaining as negative, and applying this procedure to all its classes. We employ these datasets as objective tasks. Each one of these is called “Photozilla-⟨positive-classname⟩”.

Regarding CelebA, we have picked the “Attractiveness” label as a subjective task, as attractiveness can be considered a subjective attribute. As for objective tasks, we have picked ten objective labels: “Wearing_Earrings”, “Eyeglasses”, “Hair[‡]”, “Wearing_Hat”, “Male”, “Wearing_Necklace”, “Wearing_Necktie”, “Straight_Hair”, “Wavy_Hair” and “Young”.

All these new datasets have 10,000 images, 70% from the positive class, and 30% from the negative class, following the same proportions as in AVA when splitting it into good/bad photos using 5 as a threshold. To perform a fair comparison, AVA has also been limited to 10,000 images. Furthermore, AVA can be solved as both a classification task (done by assigning a binary quality label depending on whether the mean score of the image is above or below 5), or as a regression task (done by predicting the 0-1 normalised mean score). We run experiments with these two variants of the reduced AVA dataset: we call them “AVA small (classification)” and “AVA small (regression)”, respectively.

[‡]The original label is “Bald”, but since the amount of photos labelled as “Bald” is too small, in order to have enough positive and negative labels to sample from this label, we had to flip it, turning it into “Hair” (not bald).

In all our experiments, we have only modified the parameters specified on Table 2, leaving all other parameters on their default values, except for both the `fill_mode` and `fill_value` parameters, for configuring translation, rotation and zoom to fill out-of-bounds pixels with white.

As for the hyperparameters, we have trained all our models for 12 epochs, since we obtain intermediate balanced accuracy results on all our models by training for these many epochs. Training for more epochs makes some models reach balanced accuracies near 1, rendering it difficult to perform a proper comparison. Furthermore, we have employed Adam as the optimiser, with a learning-rate of 10^{-3} and a decay of 10^{-8} . We have also applied automatic learning rate reduction based on the validation loss, reducing the learning-rate by 0.5 if the validation loss does not improve in 5 epochs.

For running these experiments, we have employed a NVIDIA RTX 3080 card, installed within a Ubuntu-22.04 machine. In order to have a reproducible[§] setup, we have run these experiments inside a Docker image, publicly available on DockerHub.[¶] This image, built upon the official Docker image of Tensorflow 2.10, includes PyYAML for loading experiments, and more libraries for graphics generation and dataset loading. The source code we have used for our experimentation is publicly available on GitHub.^{||}

For our experiments and figures, we have divided our datasets into train-validation-test splits, following the same proportions as in Rubio Perona et al. [32]. The test split is 8% of the full dataset. From the remaining dataset, 20% has been taken as the validation split, and the remaining part is the training split.

4.2 Experiments results

For our experiments, we fix the augmentation intensities to a given constant value, and we change the probability of augmenting each given image from 25% (25 of each 100 images seen by the models are augmentations of the originals) to 100% (all seen images are augmentations of the

originals), also including the probability of 0%, corresponding to the baseline models trained on just the original images. For these experiments, we run two different scenarios, by leaving the intensity fixed to either low intensity or high intensity. **Note that AutoAugment is always applied as-is, its internal parameters are not modified except for the probability of applying this technique. In all subsequent experiments, AutoAugment is considered to be a high-intensity technique.**

4.2.1 Low intensity

Firstly, we fix the intensity of our augmentation techniques at their smallest values, as indicated in Table 2. It is expected that, by producing smaller variations of the original images, the effects of the different augmentation techniques will be smaller than when applied with more intensity, as there will be a small amount of variation with respect to the original datasets.

Table 3 shows the results of these experiments, given as differences with respect to the baselines, averaged across augmentation probabilities of 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%. For a better analysis, these same results, in boxplot format, are shown on the left side of Figure 5. All these results are shown aggregated in five different dataset groups: **AVA small (classification and regression)**, all the Photozilla tasks, CelebA-attractive, and all the other CelebA tasks we have trained upon; for more fine-grained results, please consult A.

As it can be observed in the results for **both AVA small variants**, both in the tables and in the figures, save for some small peaks, almost all augmentation techniques achieve worse results. Flipping gets the exact same results. Aesthetics is a subjective matter, so it is natural that most photometric/geometric augmentation techniques degrade the aesthetics of images, and thus, their groundtruth labels. However, horizontal flipping does not excessively alter the spatial composition, and it gets results close to the baseline.

As for the objective datasets, a completely different phenomenon can be observed in general: most of the augmentation techniques greatly boost the results of their respective baselines. Even if there are performance falls in some models, this is because their baselines already begin high: for example, it begins at 0.8 balanced accuracy in Photozilla-street, as it is shown in A.

[§]In the implementation of TensorFlow we are employing, the random contrast layer doesn't have a deterministic implementation, so those results may suffer slight variations.

[¶][lgleznah/tensorflow-2.9.1-gpu-yaml:v6-tf2.10](https://github.com/lgleznah/tensorflow-2.9.1-gpu-yaml:v6-tf2.10)

^{||}https://github.com/lgleznah/aqa_augmentation_study

Fig. 5 Boxplot of the balanced accuracy difference with respect to the baselines of our models trained on our dataset groups. Results shown have been aggregated across augmentation probabilities of 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%.

	Brightness	Contrast	Flip	Rotation	Translation	Zoom	AutoAugment
AVA small (classification)	-0.0191	0.0010	0.0000	-0.0127	-0.0219	0.0017	—
AVA small (regression)	-0.0347	-0.0334	0.0000	-0.0302	-0.0115	-0.0339	—
Photozilla	0.0071	0.0489	0.0000	0.0441	0.1052	0.1145	—
CelebA attractiveness	0.0643	0.0273	0.0000	0.0444	0.0639	0.0898	—
CelebA objective tasks	0.0939	0.0503	0.0000	0.0528	0.1004	0.1032	—

Table 3 Average variations with respect to the baselines of our low-intensity augmentation experiments. Results aggregated on augmentation probabilities and on dataset groups. Biggest differences per dataset are shown in bold.

Regarding CelebA, similar phenomena can be observed. However, for CelebA-attractive, the results are not as extreme as with AVA, as these tend to be better than the baseline. Nevertheless, these balanced accuracy improvements are still worse than in the objective tasks of CelebA, as the boxplot shows.

4.2.2 High intensity

Secondly, we fix the intensity of our augmentation techniques at their highest values, as indicated in Table 2. Now that augmentations are being applied more aggressively, it is expected that the effects will be more extreme, producing higher improvements and falls in balanced accuracy.

Table 4 shows the results of these experiments, again averaged across augmentation probabilities of 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%. These same results, in boxplot format, are shown on the right side of Figure 5, grouped as before.

For both AVA small variants, the results are similar to what was shown in the low-intensity scenario: save for small peaks, all augmentation techniques yield worse results.

For all the Photozilla-derived datasets, a curious phenomenon can be observed: at higher intensities, photometric techniques, represented by the two first groups of boxplots, are achieving better results. Since these techniques are being applied more aggressively, there is richer data to train upon, and these techniques are not destroying the groundtruth labels; thus, they obtain better results.

Besides this, the behaviour is essentially the same as in the low-intensity setting. Regarding AutoAugment, it has a similar behaviour to the other augmentation techniques.

4.2.3 Results analysis

Figure 6 shows the results for each dataset group and augmentation technique, aggregated across

all intensities, percentages, and datasets in each dataset group. From what these results show, it is obvious that both AVA datasets suffer the most from our employed augmentation techniques. Photographic aesthetics are very sensitive to both colour composition and spatial structure, and any variation in these is likely to degrade the aesthetics of such photos.

However, in other subjective tasks, the variations are surprisingly not as bad. For example, in CelebA-attractive, there are barely any balanced accuracy falls, and most augmentations actually improve the results, even though not as much as in all the other objective tasks. Even if both human attractiveness and photographic quality are based on aesthetic perceptions, the former is based on a more atomistic perception, while the latter is based on the holistic perception of the image.

Namely, if a face is moved, rotated, flipped or translated within a frame, up to some extent, and as long as such face stays within the frame bounds, our perceptions about the attractiveness of such person won't be excessively altered. However, when changing colour features such as brightness or contrast, this perception gets more altered, as the boxplots show. Regarding photographic aesthetics perception, as Figure 2 shows, both colour changes and spatial alterations can severely degrade the aesthetics of an otherwise pleasant photograph, since all elements of the photograph contribute to making it aesthetically pleasant, as opposed to faces, which are isolated areas within a photo.

Figure 7 gives further details on the effectiveness of each augmentation technique. As the boxplots have shown, random flipping gives the smallest variations of them all. This is logical, since randomly flipping on the horizontal or vertical axes will generate a maximum of 4 times more images than in the original dataset, whereas other techniques can theoretically generate infinitely more images. Zooming, translating and changing

Fig. 6 Boxplot of the balanced accuracy difference with respect to the baselines of our models trained on our dataset groups. Results shown have been aggregated across high and low intensities, and augmentation probabilities of 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%.

	Brightness	Contrast	Flip	Rotation	Translation	Zoom	AutoAugment
AVA small (classification)	-0.0212	-0.0168	-0.0130	-0.0337	-0.0533	-0.0132	-0.0458
AVA small (regression)	-0.0233	-0.0226	-0.0171	-0.0250	-0.0383	-0.0349	-0.0369
Photozilla	0.0960	0.1650	-0.0215	-0.0208	0.0863	0.1430	0.1140
CelebA attractiveness	0.0115	0.0738	0.0844	0.0514	0.0455	0.0920	0.0384
CelebA objective tasks	0.0890	0.0836	0.0607	0.0083	0.0572	0.0707	0.0789

Table 4 Average variations with respect to the baselines of our high-intensity augmentation experiments. Results aggregated on augmentation probabilities and on dataset groups. Biggest differences per dataset are shown in bold.

the brightness and contrast seem to be the best techniques for augmenting images, as long as these are not applied to image-holistic problems such as AQA. AutoAugment follows this same pattern: as Tables 3 and 4 show, it does not achieve good results on subjective tasks, but it achieves good results on objective tasks.

Our studied augmentation techniques have different impacts on our subjective tasks. Figure 6 shows that, for both AVA variants and attractiveness prediction, the effects are similar. This is, a technique that causes balanced accuracy to drop significantly in one of these three tasks also causes the other to obtain worse results.

Regarding why some techniques affect more significantly than others, Figure 4 gives some intuition into this phenomenon. Both photometric techniques present small worsenings for AVA and small improvements for attractiveness prediction. However, brightness augmentations achieve smaller improvements and larger worsenings than contrast augmentations. Looking at the augmented images examples, it can be seen that brightness changes tend to generate either extremely dark or extremely bright images where it is difficult to discern its contents. For contrast changes, even if the colours can get diluted towards the average colour, it is still easier to discern the contents of the image.

For geometric techniques, random flipping has very small variability in the images it can generate, so it makes sense that the balanced accuracy differences are close to 0. For rotation, as neither image aesthetics nor convolutional neural networks are rotation-invariant, it makes sense that these rotations will yield larger worsenings. With translation, as it can be seen on the augmentation examples, large chunks of the original image can end up outside the original frame, and a lot of information will be lost for predicting aesthetics, even if the spatial composition itself does not get heavily altered. Lastly, zooming augmentations

achieve surprisingly small worsenings and notorious improvements for AVA and attractiveness prediction respectively. Looking at the examples, it can be seen that zooming tends to leave a significant amount of information of the original image intact, and the central objects in these images remain central in these augmentations. While convolutional networks are not scale-invariant, they are more robust to changes in scale than to rotations, and its filters could still recognise the objects in the image without as many complications as with rotation. Besides, some specific zooms might actually improve the framing of the image, making it more aesthetically pleasant.

5 Conclusions

In this work, we have conducted a study of the effects of various common image augmentation techniques on both subjective and objective problems. Even if most augmentation techniques are commonly used in computer vision problems, these techniques don't produce the same effects for subjective problems, where even small distortions can greatly alter the aesthetic features of an image.

To validate our research objective, we have selected two subjective tasks: determining the aesthetic quality of an image and determining the attractiveness of a face. These tasks are represented by the AVA dataset for image aesthetics and a label from the CelebA dataset for facial attractiveness. Additionally, we have chosen a set of objective tasks, which involve determining whether a photograph possesses a specific style and identifying certain objective characteristics of a face. These tasks are represented by the Photozilla dataset and additional labels from the CelebA dataset.

With these datasets, we have conducted a series of experiments in which we have left fixed

Fig. 7 Average balanced accuracy difference of our studied augmentation techniques, averaged across all datasets, intensities and augmentation probabilities

augmentation intensities, and changed the probability of augmenting images from 25% to 100%. The results show that, while AVA consistently gets very little improvement and, in most cases, performance falls, the results for the objective datasets are mostly positive. The subjective task of CelebA shows little improvement, not as big as in the other CelebA objective tasks, showing how the nature of the subjective task can influence the improvements or falls. On the one hand, aesthetic assessment is a holistic task: since the aesthetics of a photo depends on the whole photo, any small perturbation will greatly alter its groundtruth label. On the other hand, attractiveness on CelebA only depends on the region of the photo containing the face, so these same perturbations will not be as significant. Based on the experimentation results, holistic problems require preliminary experiments to determine whether data augmentation will or not be beneficial. For aesthetic assessment, the results with these techniques are mostly worse; and, on a few occasions, only slightly better. Furthermore, augmenting images adds extra time to the training process.

As future work, since zooming seems to have ever-so-slightly positive effects, we would like to test more advanced augmentation techniques based on zooming on the main objects of an image. Furthermore, we would like to try other existing, more advanced augmentation techniques such as GAN-based algorithms. Finally, we would also like to find out whether these findings generalise to even more subjective computer vision tasks.

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A Fine-grained results

This appendix ** gives further details about the results shown on Section 4.

Table 5 shows the results of our experiments on low augmentation intensity, for each dataset, averaged across 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% augmentation probabilities. The first phenomenon that can be observed is the disparity between the different datasets. For example, while datasets such as Photozilla-aerial present consistent improvements, other datasets such as Photozilla-event or Photozilla-sports present no balanced accuracy improvements at all. All these datasets, while different, have been trained under the same hyperparameters to ensure a fair comparison; it is therefore natural that, being slightly different tasks, the results will vary among these.

However, for AVA, all augmentation techniques are achieving little or no improvements at all. Due to its subjective and holistic nature, augmentation techniques destroy the relationship between images and their groundtruths. This worsening effect, however, does not happen on CelebA; and even though the baseline begins at 0.5 balanced accuracy, the improvements are not as remarkable as in other CelebA tasks. Once again, attractiveness is subjective, but not holistic, as the key information for the groundtruth is mostly contained within a bounded region of the image; i.e., the face present therein.

Table 6 shows the results of our experiments on high augmentation intensity, for each dataset, averaged across 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% augmentation probability. These results show similar phenomena to what was shown in the low-intensity results, further validating these results.

**In the tables present herein, “Rotation” and “Translation” have been renamed to “Rotate” and “Move” because of the page width.

	Baseline	Brightness	Contrast	Flip	Rotation	Translation	Zoom	AutoAugment
AVA small (classification)	0.5548	0.5358	0.5558	0.5548	0.5421	0.5330	0.5566	—
AVA small (regression)	0.5366	0.5019	0.5031	0.5366	0.5064	0.5251	0.5026	—
Photozilla-aerial	0.5491	0.8003	0.6055	0.5491	0.6340	0.7202	0.7187	—
Photozilla-architecture	0.5000	0.5000	0.6801	0.5000	0.6992	0.7147	0.8403	—
Photozilla-event	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	—
Photozilla-fashion	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5995	0.7216	0.6720	—
Photozilla-food	0.7656	0.7055	0.7607	0.7656	0.7204	0.6495	0.7507	—
Photozilla-nature	0.7952	0.6954	0.6469	0.7952	0.6465	0.8260	0.7986	—
Photozilla-sports	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	—
Photozilla-street	0.8000	0.6225	0.7462	0.8000	0.7425	0.6900	0.8219	—
Photozilla-wedding	0.5000	0.5000	0.7196	0.5000	0.6932	0.8800	0.7341	—
Photozilla-wildlife	0.5000	0.6577	0.7398	0.5000	0.6155	0.7601	0.7183	—
CelebA-attractive	0.5000	0.5643	0.5273	0.5000	0.5444	0.5639	0.5898	—
CelebA-earrings	0.5000	0.5399	0.5000	0.5000	0.5537	0.5925	0.5959	—
CelebA-eyeglasses	0.5000	0.7937	0.7394	0.5000	0.6959	0.8338	0.8144	—
CelebA-hair	0.8569	0.8643	0.8398	0.8569	0.8457	0.8701	0.8715	—
CelebA-hat	0.8176	0.8283	0.7651	0.8176	0.6977	0.7720	0.8565	—
CelebA-male	0.5814	0.7222	0.7038	0.5814	0.7166	0.7604	0.7415	—
CelebA-necklace	0.5542	0.5592	0.5389	0.5542	0.5617	0.5741	0.5508	—
CelebA-necktie	0.5000	0.7085	0.6295	0.5000	0.5414	0.8045	0.6963	—
CelebA-straight hair	0.5000	0.5201	0.5118	0.5000	0.5103	0.5138	0.5225	—
CelebA-wavy hair	0.5000	0.5814	0.5569	0.5000	0.6069	0.5231	0.5729	—
CelebA-young	0.5000	0.6317	0.5281	0.5000	0.6084	0.5695	0.6195	—

Table 5 Results of our models trained on AVA and all the Photozilla one-versus-rest datasets, for both the baselines and the models trained with one augmentation technique at low intensity. Results averaged across 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% probability of augmenting a given image. Best results per dataset are shown in bold.

	Baseline	Brightness	Contrast	Flip	Rotation	Translation	Zoom	AutoAugment
AVA small (classification)	0.5548	0.5337	0.5381	0.5418	0.5212	0.5015	0.5417	0.5091
AVA small (regression)	0.5366	0.5132	0.5140	0.5194	0.5116	0.4983	0.5016	0.4997
Photozilla-aerial	0.5491	0.7765	0.7560	0.5906	0.6708	0.6316	0.7936	0.7529
Photozilla-architecture	0.5000	0.7959	0.6554	0.5000	0.5000	0.7451	0.7966	0.8679
Photozilla-event	0.5000	0.5399	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.6135
Photozilla-fashion	0.5000	0.6025	0.7664	0.5000	0.5000	0.7664	0.8321	0.6297
Photozilla-food	0.7656	0.7599	0.9003	0.6437	0.7236	0.6668	0.8048	0.7803
Photozilla-nature	0.7952	0.8245	0.8528	0.6181	0.6528	0.8732	0.7693	0.6761
Photozilla-sports	0.5000	0.5000	0.7571	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5859	0.5000
Photozilla-street	0.8000	0.6215	0.7772	0.6587	0.5497	0.6970	0.7338	0.7680
Photozilla-wedding	0.5000	0.7813	0.7560	0.5602	0.5415	0.7990	0.8160	0.6720
Photozilla-wildlife	0.5000	0.6682	0.8385	0.6234	0.5640	0.5936	0.7076	0.7896
CelebA-attractive	0.5000	0.5115	0.5738	0.5844	0.5514	0.5455	0.5920	0.5384
CelebA-earrings	0.5000	0.5287	0.5095	0.5564	0.5290	0.5090	0.5617	0.5177
CelebA-eyeglasses	0.5000	0.8150	0.8339	0.7163	0.6003	0.7635	0.7621	0.7989
CelebA-hair	0.8569	0.8477	0.8404	0.8267	0.7790	0.7940	0.7459	0.8512
CelebA-hat	0.8176	0.8126	0.8216	0.8422	0.5048	0.7577	0.7692	0.8218
CelebA-male	0.5814	0.6470	0.6729	0.6502	0.6933	0.5526	0.6863	0.7076
CelebA-necklace	0.5542	0.5611	0.5587	0.6063	0.5361	0.5655	0.5717	0.5144
CelebA-necktie	0.5000	0.8126	0.7576	0.5825	0.5718	0.7743	0.7577	0.7857
CelebA-straight hair	0.5000	0.5187	0.5006	0.5047	0.5055	0.5000	0.5034	0.5079
CelebA-wavy hair	0.5000	0.5385	0.5625	0.5678	0.5866	0.5803	0.5672	0.5344
CelebA-young	0.5000	0.6178	0.5880	0.5644	0.5865	0.5852	0.5916	0.5591

Table 6 Results of our models trained on AVA and all the Photozilla one-versus-rest datasets, for both the baselines and the models trained with one augmentation technique at high intensity. Results averaged across 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% probability of augmenting a given image. Best results per dataset are shown in bold.